

Appendix S4: Sensitivity analyses (LODO, LOSO), spatial autocorrelation tests and spatial models

Fractal sampling design reveals climate and scale effects on rainforest bird communities in central Africa

Andres Angulo-Rubiano, Douglas Robinson, Dylan Craven, Francis Njie Motombi, Sergei Bobo Kadiri, Holger Kreft, Matthias Waltert

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LODO AND LOSO tests: To evaluate the robustness of climatic effects and control for spatial dependencies in our analyses, we conducted a series of sensitivity and spatial diagnostics. We first applied *Leave-One-Site-Out (LOSO)* and *Leave-One-Dataset-Out (LODO)* cross-validation procedures to assess how strongly individual sites or datasets influenced the estimated relationships between climatic predictors and community attributes (alpha diversity, abundance, and biomass). These analyses allowed us to verify the stability and consistency of the model coefficients across spatial strata of the gradient. Each point shows the estimated effect (slope/coefficient) after leaving out one site (LOSO) or one dataset/subset (LODO). The vertical dash line at zero marks no effect. Error bars are 95% CIs. If most leave-one-out estimates are on the same side of zero (all positive or all negative), the direction of the relationship is robust.

Spatial autocorrelation tests and spatial models

We then tested for spatial autocorrelation in model residuals using multiscale Moran's I statistics at α - (0.3 km), β - (0.9 km), and regional- (600 km) scales. Finally, we implemented spatially explicit models incorporating smooth geographic terms to account for potential spatial structure. Comparing non-spatial and spatial model outputs provided a formal check of whether climatic effects remained significant after accounting for spatial autocorrelation.

Figure S1. Pairwise correlations among climatic predictors used in the models. Heatmap showing Pearson correlation coefficients between mean annual rainfall, precipitation seasonality, mean annual temperature, and temperature seasonality. Color intensity reflects the strength and direction of correlations (blue = negative, red = positive).

FIGURE S2 LOSO analysis for the effects MAP on alpha diversity (size-standardized Hill-numbers)

Rarefied diversity — MAP (LOSO)

Points = estimate; bars = 95% CI; linear rainfall term only

FIGURE S3 LOSO analysis for the effects MAT on size-standardized Hill numbers

Rarefied diversity — MAT

LOSO; points = estimate, bars = 95% CI

FIGURE S4 LOSO analysis for the effects of PS on alpha diversity (size-standardized Hill-numbers)

Rarefied diversity — Precipitation seasonality (PS)

LOSO; points = smooth-term test statistic (F/χ^2); filled = $p < 0.05$

FIGURE S5 LOSO analysis for the effects TS on alpha diversity (size-standardized Hill-numbers)

FIGURE S6 LOSO analysis for the effects of MAP, MAT, PS, TS, on Aggregated community Abundance (ACA).

FIGURE S7 LOSO analysis for the effects of MAP, MAT, PS, TS, on Aggregated community biomass (ACB).

LODO ANALYSIS

FIGURE S8 LODO analysis for the effects of MAP on size-standardized Hill numbers

Notes: For q=1 both estimates (lower) and quadratic terms (upper) are shown. For q = 0–1, points and bars represent linear rainfall coefficients \pm 95% confidence intervals. For q = 2, GAM smooth terms are summarized by their test statistics because cross-validated smooths do not yield single coefficient estimates or confidence intervals.

FIGURE S9 LODO analysis for the effects of MAP on aggregated community abundance (ACA).

FIGURE S10 LODO analysis for the effects of MAP on aggregated community biomass (ACB).

Spatial autocorrelation tests

Moran's I Multiscale Spatial Autocorrelation Report

This report summarizes the results of multiscale Moran's I analyses for residuals from non-spatial and spatial models applied to abundance, biomass, and diversity (size-standardized Hill numbers q_2). SAC analysis, spatial GAMs were fitted only for $q = 2$, whereas $q = 0-1$ were modeled using linear mixed-effects models. Three spatial scales were tested: α (alpha plots) (0.3 km), β (beta clusters) (0.9 km), and regional (between sites) (600 km).

Table S1 Summary of Moran's I Results

Model	scale	tests	sig	mean_I	Response
Non-spatial	alpha	3	3	0.1668	Abundance
Non-spatial	beta	3	1	0.0632	Abundance
Non-spatial	regional	3	0	-0.0085	Abundance
Spatial	alpha	3	0	0.043	Abundance
Spatial	beta	3	0	-0.0626	Abundance
Spatial	regional	3	0	-0.0088	Abundance
Non-spatial	alpha	3	0	0.0901	Biomass
Non-spatial	beta	3	0	0.0181	Biomass
Non-spatial	regional	3	0	-0.0087	Biomass
Spatial	alpha	3	0	0.0536	Biomass
Spatial	beta	3	0	-0.0221	Biomass
Spatial	regional	3	0	-0.0085	Biomass
Non-spatial	alpha	3	3	0.1801	size-standardized Hill numbers q_2
Non-spatial	beta	3	3	0.2179	size-standardized Hill numbers q_2
Non-spatial	regional	3	3	-0.0035	size-standardized

					Hill numbers q2
Spatial	alpha	3	0	-0.0412	size- standardized Hill numbers q2
Spatial	beta	3	0	-0.0033	size- standardized Hill numbers q2
Spatial	regional	3	0	-0.0086	size- standardized Hill numbers q2

Notes: Across all response variables, Moran's I values were small ($|I| < 0.2$) and mostly non-significant ($p > 0.05$) after incorporating spatial smooth terms. Non-spatial models showed moderate positive autocorrelation at the α -scale (0.3 km), especially for abundance, indicating local spatial clustering of residuals. However, spatial models effectively removed this structure, resulting in Moran's I ≈ 0 across all scales.

Spatial Models Diagnostics and Sensitivity Analyses

Spatially explicit models were implemented to assess the robustness of climatic effects and evaluate potential spatial autocorrelation (SAC) in model residuals. For each community property (alpha diversity, abundance, and biomass), two sets of models were fitted: a non-spatial model and a spatial model incorporating a smooth term of geographic coordinates (longitude, latitude). Mixed-effect and generalized additive models (GAMs) were used with family distributions appropriate to each response variable: negative binomial (abundance), Gamma (biomass), and Gaussian (diversity). Random effects accounted for hierarchical structure across sites and beta clusters.

Table S2 Abundance Spatial Models

Response	Predictor	Model	Estimate	StdError	Statistic	p_value	Moran_I	Moran_p
Abundance	mean_rainfall_gradient	Non-spatial	-0.0668	0.0194	-3.4423	0.0006	-0.007	nan

Abundance	mean_rainfall_gradient	Spatial	1.4711	1.1158	1.3185	0.1873	-0.007	nan
Abundance	mean_temp_gradient	Non-spatial	-0.0225	0.0362	-0.6219	0.534	-0.007	nan
Abundance	mean_temp_gradient	Spatial	-0.0421	0.3245	-0.1299	0.8967	-0.007	nan
Abundance	temp_seasonality_c_worldclim	Non-spatial	-0.0752	0.0192	-3.9282	0.0001	-0.007	nan
Abundance	temp_seasonality_c_worldclim	Spatial	-0.1253	0.2238	-0.5597	0.5757	-0.007	nan

Table S3 Biomass Spatial Models

Response	Predictor	Model	Estimate	StdError	Statistic	p_value	Moran_I	Moran_p
Biomass	mean_rainfall_gradient	Non-spatial	-0.0052	0.0483	-0.1072	0.9146	-0.007	nan
Biomass	mean_rainfall_gradient	Spatial	4.5235	1.8117	2.4969	0.0125	-0.007	nan
Biomass	mean_temp_gradient	Non-spatial	0.0538	0.0432	1.2452	0.2131	-0.007	nan
Biomass	mean_temp_gradient	Spatial	-0.3635	0.3739	-0.9722	0.331	-0.007	nan
Biomass	temp_seasonality_c_worldclim	Non-spatial	-0.0466	0.0421	-1.1061	0.2687	-0.007	nan

		spatial						
Biomass	temp_seasonality_c_worldclim	Spatial	-0.0141	0.1077	-0.131	0.8958	-0.007	nan

Table S4 size-standardized Hill numbers (q_2) Spatial Models for alpha diversity

Response	Predictor	Model	Estimate	StdError	Statistic	p_value	Moran_I	Moran_p
Diversity rarefied (q_2)	mean_rainfall_gradient	Non-spatial	0.3347	0.5864	0.5708	0.5681	-0.007	nan
Diversity rarefied (q_2)	mean_rainfall_gradient	Spatial	-45.4421	22.3049	-2.0373	0.0416	-0.007	nan
Diversity rarefied (q_2)	mean_temp_gradient	Non-spatial	-2.1919	0.5576	-3.9313	0.0001	-0.007	nan
Diversity rarefied (q_2)	mean_temp_gradient	Spatial	-1.9219	0.8756	-2.1949	0.0282	-0.007	nan
Diversity rarefied (q_2)	temp_seasonality_c_worldclim	Non-spatial	1.3969	0.5753	2.4282	0.0152	-0.007	nan
Diversity rarefied (q_2)	temp_seasonality_c_worldclim	Spatial	-2.1657	0.9639	-2.2469	0.0246	-0.007	nan

Notes: We caution that changes in the magnitude or direction of coefficients in the diversity spatial models do not imply opposite ecological effects. Because climatic gradients and geographic position are spatially correlated, spatial smooth terms can absorb part of the climatic signal. The key criterion for interpretation is whether spatial autocorrelation in

residuals is removed (Moran's $I \approx 0$), indicating that climatic effects remain robust after accounting for spatial structure. Because dominance-weighted diversity ($q = 2$) showed clear nonlinear spatial responses, spatial GAMs were fitted only for $q = 2$; $q = 0-1$ were adequately captured by linear mixed-effects models.